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DESIGN CONCEPT OF VISUAL MESSAGES BASED ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF BRAND IDENTITY

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Abstract

Visual information design concept based on brand identification can help enterprises achieve consistency, identification and differentiation in brand communication, and enhance brand recognition and influence. This study also puts forward some practical suggestions, such as rational use of brand logo, color, font and image elements, and strengthening the application of visual information design in brand identity. This study provides a useful reference for the theory and practice of visual information design and has important guiding significance for the decision-making and practice of enterprises in brand communication.

Keywords: Brand identification, visual information design, brand communication, consistency, differentiation.

Introduction. Brand visual identity is a very important part of brand construction, through visual elements to express the specific image and identity of the brand, so as to enhance the recognition and memory of the brand. Designers need to take people as the core and combine life, residence, psychology and other factors to carry out rational creative activities, so as to achieve the purpose of communicating the relationship between man and nature and between man and society. Through careful design and execution of the visual identity plan, the brand can win the loyalty and trust of consumers, which is conducive to improving the brand awareness and reputation, and also helps the brand differentiate from competitors, so as to gain a larger share in the market. Therefore, in the process of brand building, the importance of visual identity can not be ignored. When a set of complete visual recognition system is constructed, its image can be more clearly presented in front of the public. Visual elements include logos, colors, fonts, etc., which can not only convey the basic message of the brand, but more importantly, inspire people's emotional resonance. A successful brand visual identity system can not only help consumers quickly identify the brand, but also stimulate consumers' sense of trust and identity for the brand [1]. Therefore, in the process of brand building, enterprises need to make long-term investment in visual design and continuously optimize the brand visual identity system to maintain the brand's competitive advantage.

Visual information concept:

Visual information design is the art and science of using graphics, colors, typography, images and other visual elements to convey information, express meaning and arouse audience interest. It plays an important role in advertising, brand identity, packaging, websites, social media, logos, posters, books, magazines and other communication media. Through reasonable design and layout, through the organic combination and

expression of visual elements, to help people better understand and accept information. It can communicate emotions, ideas, values, brand image and more through colors, shapes, images, fonts, typography and other visual elements. Focus not only on aesthetics and attractive appearance, but also on the effectiveness of the message and the needs of the target audience. It needs to take into account the cognitive, cultural, emotional and behavioural characteristics of the target audience in the design to ensure that the design can effectively convey the message and arouse the interest and resonance of the audience. Eyes, ears, mouth, nose and skin, the five sensory organs of human beings feel information in different forms. They are receivers of information. Everything they receive is information (vision, hearing, taste, smell and touch). Compared with other sensory information designs, visual information design has unique advantages and importance [2].

The practical application of visual information design in brand identity

Brand identity plays an important role in shaping brand image. Brand recognition refers to forming a unique brand image and recognition system through a series of visual elements, such as logo, logo type, logo color, logo font, etc., so as to help consumers recognize and identify the brand in the market. The visual information design can combine, typeset, color match and other visual elements of brand identification to create a visual harmony, consistency and attractive brand image [3]. Brand identity can achieve the following functions through visual information design:

1. Build the brand image: The visual information design of brand identity can help build the image of the brand, so as to establish the cognition, impression and emotional connection of the brand in the minds of consumers. Through reasonable design, a brand can present a unique visual style and brand personality, which

can distinguish it from its competitors in the market and form a unique brand identification.

2. Improve brand identification: the visual information design of brand identification can make the brand more easily recognized and recognized by consumers in the market. Consistent visual element design can help consumers quickly identify brands in different media, platforms and scenes, thus strengthening brand recognition and increasing brand exposure and memory.

3. Convey brand value and information: The visual information design of brand identity can convey brand values, positioning and information through the combination and expression of visual elements. For example, the color, font, shape and other design of the logo can convey the emotion, culture and product characteristics of the brand, so as to guide consumers' cognitive and emotional connection to the brand.

4. Improve user experience: The visual information design of brand identification can provide users with good visual experience, so as to improve their goodwill and closeness to the brand. Reasonable design can make the brand more beautiful, easy to understand and pleasant in the display of user contact points, so as

to improve user experience and satisfaction of the brand.

Brand identity plays an important role in shaping the visual information design of the brand. Through reasonable design and combination, it can help the establishment of brand image, the improvement of recognition, the transmission of value and information and the improvement of user experience. When using visual information design to build brand image, enhance brand recognition, and convey brand value and information, the following are some specific methods and steps:

Brand logo is the core element of brand image. Through the design of a unique, concise and recognizable logo, consumers can form an impression of the brand. Logo design should consider the core value, positioning and characteristics of the brand, and choose appropriate shape, color, font and other elements to express. For example, the shape of the logo can be associated with the industry, product or service of the brand, the color can match the sentiment and tonality of the brand, and the font can match the style and positioning of the brand (Fig.1).

Fig.1 Apple Logo

Color plays an important role in the visual information design of a brand, which can convey the emotion, atmosphere and characteristics of the brand through the selection and collocation of colors. Different

ent colors have different associations and emotions psychologically, so it is very important to choose the right colors and color schemes in the visual information design of the brand. For example, some fast food brands often use red to convey energy and excitement (Fig.2).

Fig.2 KFC

Graphic and image design can convey brand information and value through shapes, lines, patterns and other elements. For example, by using specific graphic elements in the visual design of a brand, such as abstract patterns, geometric shapes or unique lines, it can express the brand's characteristics such as innovation, vitality or stability. These graphic elements can be used in different design elements, such as logo, packaging, advertising, etc., so as to form a unique brand image.

Font and typographic design are also very important in the delivery of visual information of a brand. By choosing the right font and typography, you can convey the brand's image, style and positioning. For example, choosing a modern, concise font can convey the modernity and simplicity of the brand, while choosing a classical, gorgeous font can convey the traditional and high-end image of the brand. In the layout design, we should also consider the typesetting style and layout consistent with the brand image.

In the visual information design of the brand, the use of appropriate pictures and visual elements can also effectively convey the brand value and information. Through the selection of images and visual elements in line with the brand image, the characteristics, strengths and core values of the brand can be expressed in the design. For example, if the brand emphasizes nature and environmental values, images and visual elements such as natural landscape and ecological elements can be used to convey the environmental protection and sustainable development concept of the brand. If the brand focuses on innovation and technology, it can choose scientific and technological elements, digital images, etc., to highlight the brand's technological leadership.

In order to enhance brand recognition, visual information design should maintain a consistent design style. This includes maintaining consistent design elements such as colors, fonts, graphics and images across different design elements to form a unified image of the brand. Consistent design style can help consumers identify and remember the brand more easily, thus enhancing brand recognition and impression.

Brand visual information design should be applied in multiple channels and media, including brand logo, packaging, advertising, website, social media, etc. Consistent design styles and elements in different design applications can form brand consistency and coherence. This helps to strengthen the brand recognition, so that consumers can easily identify the brand in different channels, and form the impression and cognition of the brand.

Uniqueness and innovation are very important in visual information design. A unique and innovative design can arouse consumers' interest and attention, thus enhancing brand recognition and impression. By incorporating unique and innovative elements into the design, the brand can stand out in a competitive market and convey the unique value and message of the brand.

In visual information design, the core values and information of the brand should be accurately transmitted. The design should be in line with the brand's positioning, characteristics and target audience to convey the brand's core values and message. For example, if

the brand focuses on quality and reliability, the design should emphasize these characteristics, such as the use of high quality materials and designs in the packaging, to convey the brand's quality and reliability.

Through visual information design, a brand can create a unique image, enhance brand recognition, and deliver brand value and information [4]. This can be achieved by choosing appropriate design elements such as colors, fonts, graphics and images, maintaining a consistent design style, multi-channel application design, unique and innovative design, and accurately conveying the core values and messages of the brand. A successful visual information design can make consumers have a deep impression on the brand, enhance brand recognition and goodwill, and thus bring more brand loyalty and consumers' willingness to choose the brand.

Influence of brand identity development on visual information design

As an important part of brand management, brand identity aims to convey and show the personality and values through a series of consistent visual elements [5]. As a key element of brand identity, visual information design is constantly affected by the development and changes of brand identity, which are as follows:

1). Diversified and personalized design: With the increasingly fierce competition in the brand market, brand identity requires more diversity and individuation in the design to attract and retain the target consumers. Visual information design also reflects a more diversified and personalized trend in brand identity, including the innovative and personalized application of color, graphics, fonts and other elements, to convey the uniqueness and individuation of the brand with a unique design language.

2). Responsive design: With the popularity of digital media and the rapid development of mobile Internet, there is an increasing demand for brand display on different media and platforms. Therefore, visual information design needs to be more flexible and responsive to adapt to the display needs of different screen sizes, devices and platforms, and maintain a consistent brand image [6].

3). User experience-oriented design: User experience plays an increasingly important role in brand identity, and brands need to create good user experience through visual information design. Visual information design needs to consider the user's emotion, cognition and behavior in the process of brand contact, in order to provide pleasant, concise and easy-to-understand design, so as to enhance the user's goodwill and affinity for the brand.

4). Social media and Internet communication have a profound impact on brand identity. Brands need to display a consistent visual image on social media platforms and attract and guide users' attention through visual information design. Visual information design needs to be adapted to different social media platforms in order to conform to the characteristics of each platform and user habits.

5). Sustainability and social responsibility are getting more and more attention in modern brand management. Brands need to communicate their environmental

and social concerns and commitment through visual message design. This may include using environmentally friendly materials in the design, adopting sustainable colors and graphics, or incorporating socially responsible elements in the logo, such as charity activities, social missions, etc., to demonstrate the brand's focus on sustainability and social responsibility.

6). With the acceleration of globalization and the rise of cultural diversity, brands need to consider ways of conveying visual information under different cultural backgrounds in their design. Brand identity needs to be consistent across regions and cultures, as well as adapted to different cultural aesthetics and communication methods to ensure brand recognition and acceptance on a global scale.

7). With the continuous development of science and technology, visual information design in brand identity is also affected by technological innovation. For example, technological innovations such as virtual reality, augmented reality and dynamic logos can be applied in brand identification to bring a more interactive and innovative visual experience to the brand.

The development of brand identity has a continuous impact on visual information design, including diverse and personalized design, responsive design, user experience-oriented design, the impact of social media and Internet communication, the concern of sustainability and social responsibility, cultural diversity and globalization, and the application of technological innovation. Are constantly shaping and evolving the visual image of the brand and the way of communication.

The promotion of brand identity development to visual information design

Brand visual design simply means that the brand's internal temperament and character can be visualized and visualized through design. The development of a brand cannot be separated from the environment. Communicate the relationship between human and nature, human and society through visual communication design: improve human living conditions through the design of space environment, and make material and spirit integrated in the design process, which is the primary task of visual design. In the design, color revolves around people, set life, living, psychological, visual winter factors to do a rational creative activity. This kind of activity in man, nature and society in order to achieve harmony between one and one.

Therefore, visual design should maximize a kind of affinity between man and nature, man and man, and man and society, so that it can build a bridge between the three will dredging and information exchange. Human - natural society is the coordinate point of visual design system. To be exact, it is to transform visual design system into product system and judge its advantages and disadvantages in environmental quality by looking at its affinity and disaffinity with the acceptor.

While developing and designing the corporate image, the concept of personalized brand image identification system is the essence of brand personality in the brand identification system. With the unification of technology and the strengthening of the trend of product quality convergence, the enterprise concept can

more uniquely and exclusively represent itself. Behavior identification, visual identification and idea identification are closely linked, therefore, the uniqueness of corporate concept also defines the relevant characteristics of corporate behavior display and visual communication.

For example, the staff of Japan's Panasonic electric company provided speeches every other week and new product delivery ceremony, Thai International Airlines "baby care service", McDonald's golden arc arch door! The red wave of Coca Cola has formed unique behavioral signs and visual symbols, which is a unique display of its corporate philosophy. Uniqueness becomes the content of easy image recognition in the process of communication, the important manifestation of visual identity personalization is "unity" or "consistency", which means that inside and outside the enterprise, above and below maintain the consistency and coordination of operation, attitude and image. Only unification can highlight the personality of the brand, strengthen the impression of the public, and form the visibility and reputation of the enterprise. In brand identity system, newspaper is widely used for brand information dissemination. Magazines, TV, radio, POP and other mass media. In addition, human and physical media are often used. Human body language is the language displayed by human body as the medium. It conveys information through human actions, expressions and attitudes. Physical media refers to the intermediary that disseminates corporate ideas by recording information on physical objects, usually including products, symbols, public relations gifts, buildings, uniforms, etc. Products can carry product brand, trademark, packaging, internal quality, pre-sale and after-sales service and other information. Symbol is a kind of artifact reflecting corporate culture, is a carrier to spread the spirit of enterprise, its shape can be animal, plant or other shapes [7]. Public relations gifts are the media to publicize the corporate image or product image and communicate the target public relations. The uniform clothing of enterprise employees can give people a sense of wholeness, so that people have a sense of rigorous business service and strong sense of discipline [8]. In addition, some business supplies, office equipment, equipment, transportation and other media related to the enterprise itself also become a necessary supplement for the dissemination of enterprise information.

Conclusions. The concept of visual information design based on brand identity:

1. Consistency: Brand identity emphasizes consistent visual elements in different media and channels, including brand logo, color, font, graphics, etc. In visual information design, the concept of consistency is also important, that is, to maintain consistent visual elements in the process of information transmission, so that information is easier to recognize and remember.

2. Brand identification usually emphasizes concise, clear and easily recognizable visual elements. In visual information design, the concept of simplicity is also applicable, that is, concise images, graphics, symbols, typesetting and other ways to make information intuitive and clear, reduce redundancy and interference,

and improve the readability and understandability of information.

3. Brand identity pursues uniqueness and innovation, which can arouse the interest and attention of observers. In visual information design, creative ideas are equally important, that is, to make information more attractive and bright through innovative and unique design methods, so as to arouse the interest and attention of observers and improve the effect of information transmission.

4. Brand identification needs to consider the target market and audience to ensure brand recognition and attractiveness. In visual information design, the goal-oriented concept is also applicable, that is, according to the target of information transmission and the characteristics of the audience, the selection of appropriate visual elements and design methods to ensure that the information can produce a good communication effect for the target audience.

5. Brand identity emphasizes user experience, which enables users to generate positive emotions and cognition when they contact the brand. In visual information design, the concept of user experience is equally important, that is, considering the perception and cognitive characteristics of users, design the way and form of information transmission, so that users can easily understand and interpret the information, and obtain a good user experience.

The above are some ideas of visual information design from the perspective of brand identity. These ideas can be used as a reference in the actual visual information design to achieve more effective and successful information transmission effect.

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